

Fedra Final Technical Report: proof-of-concept pipelines for Porto@IRIS and OpenAlex metadata linking

Task 1. Reporting Period M6 – M12

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Abstract. This technical report documents the final deliverable of the FEDRA project, Task 1, which aims to support the integration of the Politecnico di Torino research information system with external open scholarly infrastructures within a FAIR-aligned institutional metadata lake. We describe a proof-of-concept pipeline to reconcile author and work records stored in institutional databases with corresponding entities in OpenAlex, combining identifier-based linking (ORCID/DOI) with similarity-based matching when identifiers are missing or inconsistent. We report validation experiments on curated samples and provide summary statistics on matching performance. Finally, we compare the availability of works across OpenAlex and Scopus for a selected subset of researchers, discussing observed coverage gaps and recurrent edge cases relevant for institutional metadata enrichment and quality control.

Keywords: Data lake · Metadata lake · FAIR principles · Open Search · Open Science · CoARA.

1 Introduction

The FEDRA project (*An institutional FAIR data lake for transparent, inclusive, and reproducible Research Assessment*) aims to design and validate an institutional research information data lake aligned with the FAIR principles, to support accountable, transparent, and reproducible research assessment. The project builds on the Politecnico di Torino Research Registry, which integrates information from multiple internal databases covering key research dimensions (e.g., projects, proposals, contracts, patents, publications, datasets, and personnel records), and provides governed access to these data for analytics and meta-research.

This report constitutes the final technical deliverable for Task 1 and extends the technical work reported in the first project deliverable deposited on Zenodo [1]. While the previous deliverable focused on requirements analysis and initial architectural design, here we document the implementation and evaluation of a proof-of-concept pipeline to integrate and validate research output metadata across institutional sources and open scholarly infrastructures. In particular, we address the practical problem of entity reconciliation (authors and works) between institutional records and OpenAlex, and we provide quantitative evidence on coverage and data quality issues relevant for a FAIR-aligned institutional metadata lake.

The core technical contributions of this deliverable are: (i) an author-matching workflow to associate institutional researchers with OpenAlex author profiles, leveraging ORCID when available and DOI-based co-occurrence signals otherwise; (ii) a work-matching workflow to align institutional publications with OpenAlex records using DOI-based and similarity-based (title-, year-, and institution-based) strategies; and (iii) an empirical assessment of OpenAlex coverage compared to Scopus for a curated subset of Politecnico di Torino researchers.

The remainder of the report is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the data sources, the experimental setup, and the matching methodology. Section 3 reports the experimental results for author matching, work matching, and the comparative coverage analysis between OpenAlex and Scopus. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the main outcomes.

2 Methods

The working environment in which the experiments were conducted is a virtual machine running the FreeBSD operating system, accessed via SSH connection. A MySQL server installed on the same virtual machine stores data on authors and publications, extracted from the IRIS and Scopus databases.

All information obtained from OpenAlex was downloaded via the public OpenAlex API.

The programming language used is Python 3.13.0. The software repository containing the scripts developed for this project is publicly available [2].

2.1 Data sources

The data pipelines of this work start from data extracted from the Politecnico di Torino IRIS databases and combine them with records retrieved from external sources (Scopus and OpenAlex) to support the enrichment of the institutional database. To this aim, we tested methods for author/work matching and for analyzing coverage across the different data sources. The source SQL tables used in this work are listed below with a brief description:

- *pub_ri_prodotti_base*: table containing the metadata of all university publications. For each work it contains information such as the title, a string with all authors, the year of publication, DOI code, *handle** code, etc...
- *pub_ri_prodotti_autori*: table obtained by extracting the authors of all university publications. For each author it contains personal information such as name, surname, role, *matricola*** , tax code, ORCID code, handle code of the associated work, etc...
- *dwpauiper_vista_personale_attivo*: table containing the personal data of all university staff.
- *iris_ods_ll_rm_person*: subset of authors in *dwpauiper_vista_personale_attivo* who have manually entered their own *authorID**** in the institutional platform.

* Each work in the IRIS databases has a unique identifying code called *handle*.

** Each author in the IRIS databases has a unique identifying code called *matricola*.

*** Each author in the Scopus databases has a unique identifying code called *authorID*.

2.2 Entity reconciliation strategy and definitions

This deliverable addresses the practical problem of reconciling institutional entities (authors and works) with OpenAlex records. Whenever persistent identifiers are available (ORCID for authors; DOI for works), they are treated as high-confidence keys for matching. In the absence of identifiers, we rely on similarity-based heuristics applied to normalized strings (names and titles) and on lightweight decision rules to identify candidate matches.

2.2.1 Calculation of Similarity Index Between Name and Surname Pairs The objective is to estimate the similarity between two author names or two sets of authors, even when they appear in different forms, obtaining a score from 0 to 1. When there are two lists of authors, the algorithm attempts to match the most similar ones in order to obtain an overall measure of similarity. The algorithm follows these steps:

1. **String normalization and initial extraction:** each name/surname is transformed to lowercase, punctuation marks are removed, and common titles and qualifications are eliminated (e.g., Prof., Dott., etc...). The result is a sequence of relevant words, typically name and surname. From the words obtained after normalization, the initials are then extracted, useful for recognizing abbreviated versions of names/surnames.
2. **Calculation of similarity between two authors:** the lists of significant words of each name/surname are compared by dividing the number of words shared between the names/surnames of the two authors by the number of the total word set of both names/surnames. This results in a number between 0 and 1, where 1 indicates an identical case. Further adjustments are applied when the initials of the name coincide, or when the surname coincides.
3. **Comparison between two lists of authors:** a matrix containing the similarities between authors on the two lists is created. Subsequently, the pairs with the highest score are selected, using an incremental strategy, avoiding repetitions. The sum of the selected scores is then normalised by dividing it by the greater of the two list lengths, thus obtaining a final value between 0 and 1.

2.2.2 Calculation of Similarity Index Between Titles of Two Publications The objective is to estimate how similar two publication titles are, even when they appear in different forms, obtaining a score from 0 to 1. The approach is the same as the previous case, but simplified. In fact, after the extraction of the relevant words, the final value is already calculated as in point 2 of section 2.2.1, without extraction and use of initials.

2.2.3 Decision rules and terminology. Throughout the report we use the following terminology: a *compatible match* indicates that an institutional record and an OpenAlex record can be linked with high confidence (typically via ORCID/DOI or a very high similarity score), whereas a *similar match* indicates a plausible link supported by similarity-based evidence but requiring more caution. Thresholds used to operationalize these categories are introduced within the corresponding author- and work-matching experiments.

2.2.4 Reproducibility and scope note. All scripts used in the experiments are available in the accompanying software repository [2]. Because the metadata infrastructures (OpenAlex and Scopus) are continuously updated, the exact results of API-based experiments may vary over time even when the institutional source tables remain unchanged. Unless otherwise stated, OpenAlex and Scopus queries and outputs reported in this deliverable were collected in January 2026.

3 Experiments and results

3.1 Data Matching Between IRIS and OpenAlex

This section reports the experiments aimed at linking authors and works extracted from the institutional database (Porto@IRIS) to corresponding entities in OpenAlex. As highlighted below, missing identifiers and data quality issues, both in institutional records and in OpenAlex, can make matching non-trivial. The main issues encountered during the experiments are listed below:

- A. Authors without ORCID identifier or with corrupted ORCID in institutional databases.
- B. Authors with multiple ORCID associated.
- C. Authors without *matricola*.
- D. Authors with inconsistent name and surname across various platforms.
- E. Multiple OpenAlex profiles associated with the same author.
- F. Author absent in OpenAlex.
- G. Works without DOI identifier or with corrupted DOI in institutional databases.
- H. Works with multiple DOI associated.
 - I. Multiple occurrences of a work on OpenAlex.
 - J. Work absent in OpenAlex.
- K. Spelling errors or lack of essential information in some authors/works on OpenAlex.

Regarding point D, searches were performed using the author name and surname strings. Unfortunately, these fields are not always reported consistently across different platforms. In particular, some fields are sometimes abbreviated (e.g., N. Surname) or a title is inserted (e.g., Prof. Name Surname). This is further complicated by the possible presence of second names or surnames, and the possibility of spelling errors.

Regarding point K, errors or missing information are heterogeneous, mostly of sporadic nature. Frequent cases include missing ORCID/DOI identifiers, or the absence of a given name and surname among the authors list of a work.

3.1.1 Author Matching For this experiment, we used the source SQL table *pub_ri_prodotti_autori*. For each author in this table, the objective is to find the associated OpenAlex profile, if any.

Fig. 1: High-level overview of the data pipeline for the author-matching algorithm. For the sake of clarity, the figure omits the multiple matching attempts performed by the algorithm across candidate OpenAlex author profiles. For details, see the workflow steps reported in the text.

For authors with a valid ORCID field, matching was very simple as an API call with the code itself as a filter was sufficient. For the remaining authors, we adopted an alternative strategy to identify the most plausible OpenAlex profile. The workflow followed for each author, identified by *matricola*, is as follows:

1. API call to the OpenAlex servers, filtering by the author's name, surname and Polito ROR and saving the OpenAlex profiles returned as the output. If no accounts are found, the algorithm stops.
2. Extraction, via *matricola*, of all works with DOI of the author from the table *pub_ri_prodotti_base*. If no works with a DOI are found, the algorithm stops.
3. For each of the works extracted in point 2, an API call is made to OpenAlex servers via the DOI. If the call returns a result, the OpenAlex authors of the OpenAlex work are saved.
4. Making a ranking of the most frequent OpenAlex profiles extracted in point 3.
5. First matching attempt searching for the OpenAlex profile extracted in point 1 which OpenAlex ID matches with the one of the top three OpenAlex profiles in the ranking. This is called **compatible match**.
6. If no results are found in the previous point, a second matching attempt, called **similar match**, is done. It consists in finding the first author in the ranking, going in descending order, whose name and surname has a similarity score higher or equal to a selected threshold with the name and surname of one of the OpenAlex authors extracted in point 1.
7. If no results are found in the previous point, the procedure selects the first OpenAlex profile in the ranking. This is called **no compatible match**.

The need to select the top three accounts with the most occurrences and to eventually calculate a similarity index, as indicated in points 5 and 6, in addition to improving the robustness of the algorithm, stems from some edge cases in which the author under examination, unexpectedly, does not appear first in the occurrence ranking (a practical example is an author "Name_A Surname_A" who has often collaborated with an author "Name_B Surname_B" during their career and whose name appears in multiple formats. The result is that "Name_B Surname_B" will appear as the author with the most occurrences).

It is important to note that a DOI-based analysis is performed for each author, even if a single OpenAlex profile has been found or when ORCID filtering has been used. This provides an additional consistency check for the algorithm.

We tested the algorithm on a sample dataset made of all the authors who published at least one work in 1997 and for whom the ORCID is missing in the IRIS database. The dataset includes 182 authors. As shown in the tables below, a match was found for 131 of them; for the remaining 51 authors, no OpenAlex profile was found. We observed that similarity scores lower than 0.7 resulted in unreliable matches. Therefore, 0.7 was selected as the threshold used in step 6. Finally, we manually verified, author by author, that the matched OpenAlex authors were correct, supporting the efficiency of the algorithm. Additional statistics are provided in the tables below for a deeper investigation.

Metric	Value
Total authors processed	182
Authors with OpenAlex profiles found	131 (71.98%)
Authors without OpenAlex profiles found	51
Authors with single OpenAlex profile found	101
Authors with multiple OpenAlex profiles found	30
Average OpenAlex profiles found per author	1.26

Table 1: Overall authors statistics in authors matching experiment.

Metric	Value
Authors with compatible match found	98
Authors with similar match found	7
Authors with no compatible match	0

Table 2: Overall authors statistics divided by different match types, in relation to authors matching experiment.

3.1.2 Work matching For this experiment, we used the SQL table *pub_ri_prodotti_base* as the source table. Each publication is identified by a unique `handle`. The goal is to find the corresponding OpenAlex work, if any.

For publications with a valid DOI, synchronization is straightforward and relies on a single OpenAlex API call filtering by DOI. For publications with missing or corrupted DOI, we adopt the workflow below:

1. API call to OpenAlex servers filtering by title, institution and publication year. The OpenAlex works returned as output are then saved.
2. For each OpenAlex work found in step 1, if any, a similarity score is calculated as follows:

$$score = similarity_titles * 0.5 + similarity_authors * 0.25 + similarity_publication_year * 0.25$$

where:

Fig. 2: High-level overview of the data pipeline for the work-matching algorithm. For additional details the reader can refer to Section 3.1.2

- *similarity_titles* stands for the similarity index between the publication title and the OpenAlex work title
- *similarity_authors* stands for the similarity index between the publication author string and the OpenAlex work author string
- *similarity_publication_year* stands for the similarity index between the paper publication year and the OpenAlex work publication year. It is equal to 1 when there is an exact match, and decreases towards 0 as the distance between the two numbers increases.

3. At this point, the work with the highest score is selected.

We tested the algorithm on a sample dataset made of the first 200 works, ordered by *handle*, without DOI and published in 2004. As can be seen in table 3, a match was found for 177 of them; for the remaining 23 works, no result was returned by OpenAlex, even when searching by title only. Among the 177 matched papers, 137 had a similarity score above 0.8. Manual checking indicated that similarity score lower than 0.8 resulted in unreliable matching; therefore, we used 0.8 as the threshold to define high-confidence matches.

Metric	Count	Percentage
Total works processed	200	—
Works with matches found	177	88.5%
Works not matched	23	11.5%
High confidence matches (similarity > 0.8)	137	68.5%

Table 3: Overall works statistics in works matching experiment. The entry “High confidence matches (similarity > 0.8)” refer to the number of works with match found with a similarity score higher than the reliable threshold of 0.8.

Quality Range	Count	Percentage
Perfect matches (1.0)	106	59.9%
High quality (0.9–1.0)	27	15.3%
Good quality (0.8–0.9)	4	2.3%
Moderate quality (0.7–0.8)	2	1.1%
Low quality (0.5–0.7)	7	4.0%
Poor quality (<0.5)	31	17.5%
High confidence (>0.8)	137	77.4%

Table 4: Distribution of similarity scores across works matched in works matching experiment.

3.2 Work coverage comparison between OpenAlex and Scopus

This experiment evaluates the coverage of works in OpenAlex and in Scopus for a subset of Politecnico di Torino researchers. For each author, we extracted all the deposited works from Porto@IRIS and assessed whether corresponding records could be retrieved from OpenAlex and from Scopus.

To enable the Scopus comparison, we restricted the analysis to personnel records with a non-null Scopus *authorID*. Consequently, the source table used was built by combining the two tables *iris_ods_ll_rm_person* and *dupauper_vista_personale_attivo* via tax code and retaining only records with non-null *authorID*. Furthermore, we selected all personnel with birth date greater than 1950 to increase the likelihood of having an ORCID available for OpenAlex queries. The resulting dataset contains 677 people. For each author identified by *matricola*, the workflow is as follows:

1. Extract, via *matricola*, all the works of the author from the table *pub_ri_prodotti_base*.
2. API call to OpenAlex servers filtering by the author’s ORCID code and store all OpenAlex works of the retrieved OpenAlex author profile.
3. Extract all Scopus works of the author filtering by *authorID* code the Scopus database.
4. For each work of the author, a match is searched via DOI or title with the set of OpenAlex works found in point 2. If for a given work no match is found, an API call is made to OpenAlex servers via DOI or title of the work and among the OpenAlex works obtained as a result, the most reliable one is selected, if any (indeed, it is checked, via similarity index calculation, whether the author in question is present in the authors string of the OpenAlex work under examination).
5. For each work of the author, a match is searched via DOI or title with the set of Scopus works found in point 3.

The additional OpenAlex query in step 4 accounts for the possibility that OpenAlex author profiles may be incomplete or inaccurate, and that relevant works may therefore be missing from the work set returned by a profile-based query.

As can be seen in tables 5–8, among the 677 authors examined, 646 had an OpenAlex matched-work count greater than or equal to the matched-work count in Scopus. In addition, 422 authors had zero works that were matched in Scopus but not in OpenAlex, whereas the remaining 255 authors had at least one such work (2.34 works on average among those authors). Regarding the percentage of works present exclusively in Scopus, we observed that some are also present in OpenAlex, but the algorithm was unable to detect them due to new errors and issues that had not been previously considered, such as the absence of an author in the string of authors of the OpenAlex record in question. For other works, manual searches confirmed that they are not present in OpenAlex. Additional statistics are provided in the tables below for a deeper investigation. For the sake of completeness, a few more tables are reported in the Appendix.

Fig. 3: High-level overview of the data pipeline for the work-coverage algorithm. For more details the reader can refer to Section 3.2.

Statistic	Value
Total authors processed	677
Authors with ORCID	677 (100.00%)
Authors without ORCID	0 (0.00%)
Authors with Scopus ID	668 (98.67%)
Authors without Scopus ID	9 (1.33%)
Authors with OpenAlex profile	650

Table 5: Overall statistics on personnel records used in works coverage experiment. The “Authors with an OpenAlex profile” entry indicates the number of authors for whom a corresponding OpenAlex profile has been found.

Statistic	Value
Total works in IRIS database	68,961
Total works with DOI	41,331 (59.93%)
Total works matched on OpenAlex	64,143
OpenAlex match rate	93.01%
Total works matched on Scopus	44,291
Scopus match rate	64.23%

Table 6: Overall statistics on works extracted in works coverage experiment. The OpenAlex and Scopus match rates have been calculated dividing the number of works matched with the total works in IRIS database.

Statistic	Value
Authors with OA matches \geq Scopus matches	646 (95.42%)
Authors with OA matches $>$ Scopus matches	572 (84.49%)
Authors with OA matches = Scopus matches	74 (10.93%)
Authors with Scopus matches $>$ OA matches	31 (4.58%)

Table 7: Statistics on OpenAlex and Scopus work coverage in relation to the work coverage experiment. Entries such as ‘Authors with OA matches \geq Scopus matches’ refer to the number of authors for whom the number of works found in OpenAlex is greater than or equal to the number of works found in Scopus.

Statistic	Value
Authors with at least one work missing in OpenAlex	255 (36.67%)
Average number of works missing only in OpenAlex per author	2.34
Total works missing only in OpenAlex	597

Table 8: Statistics on the number of works that have been found only in Scopus and not in OpenAlex, in relation to the work coverage experiment. Note that Table 7 compares match counts per author, whereas Table 8 reports set differences (authors with at least one IRIS work matched in Scopus but not in OpenAlex); these conditions can overlap.

4 Conclusion

This deliverable reported a proof-of-concept implementation to link author and work metadata stored in institutional databases with corresponding records in OpenAlex, and to compare the availability of works across OpenAlex and Scopus for a subset of Politecnico di Torino researchers. The overall objective was to support the integration of the internal research information system with external open scholarly infrastructures within a FAIR-aligned institutional data lake.

The technical work developed and tested (i) an author-matching pipeline combining ORCID-based linking with a DOI- and title- driven fallback strategy for authors lacking ORCID, (ii) a work-matching pipeline relying on DOI when available and on similarity-based matching (mainly based on title) otherwise, and (iii) a comparative coverage analysis between OpenAlex and Scopus on a subset of researchers. Overall, the experiments show that identifier-based linking provides robust matches when persistent identifiers are present, while similarity-based approaches can recover additional matches in the absence of ORCID/DOI and enable first-order coverage comparisons across sources.

Within the scope of FEDRA, the deliverable provides an initial, documented baseline (including code, decision rules, and empirical evidence on recurrent edge cases) that can be reused and extended by future institutional initiatives or follow-up projects. Future work could benefit from scaling the analysis to larger and more heterogeneous datasets, which would likely surface additional edge cases that can be systematically incorporated into the matching logic. In addition, a complementary AI component could be explored to support deeper metadata inspection and adaptive retrieval strategies (e.g., triggering additional searches when no match is found or when similarity scores are consistently low). These directions fall outside the current project scope but are enabled by the technical outputs documented here. Finally, although the technical work focused on OpenAlex, the same reconciliation principles and similarity-based strategies can be adapted to support integration with other open platforms (e.g., OpenAIRE).

Acknowledgments

We thank Paolo Tealdi for technical support with data extraction from the Porto@IRIS repository, and Alessandra Cerato, Luigi Erriquens, Antonina Maria Marino, and Arianna Montorsi for helpful discussions.

Author Contributions

The contributions of the authors to this deliverable are outlined according to the CRediT taxonomy.

Conceptualization – M.G., F.C.; **Methodology** – M.G., F.C.; **Software** – M.G.; **Validation** – M.G.; **Formal Analysis** – M.G. F.C.; **Investigation** – M.G.; **Resources** – F.C.; **Data Curation** – M.G.; **Writing** – Original Draft – M.G.; **Writing – Review & Editing** – F.C.; all authors have read and approved the final version of this report; **Visualization** – M.G.; **Supervision** – F.C.; **Funding Acquisition** – F.C.

Funding disclaimer

The FEDRA project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Funded within the framework of the CoARA Boost Project under grant agreement No 101131826.

Appendix

The following appendix provides additional results for the coverage experiment described in Section 3.2. The first two tables report summary statistics for researchers operating in bibliometric and non-bibliometric areas, respectively. The last two tables group results by SSD code (i.e. the scientific disciplinary sector according to Italian national classification) and report two rankings: (i) academic fields ranked by the number of works not matched by the OpenAlex-based procedure, and (ii) academic fields ranked by the percentage of authors

whose number of matched works in OpenAlex is greater than or equal to the corresponding number in Scopus (both in descending order).

Statistic	Value
Total authors	505
Percentage of Authors with OA matches \geq Scopus matches	97.23%
Percentage of Authors with Scopus matches $>$ OA matches	2.77%
Percentage of Authors with at least one work missing only in OpenAlex	43.37%
Average number of works missing only in OpenAlex	2.16

Table 9: Overall statistics on personnel records from bibliometric areas used in works coverage experiment. The “Authors with an OpenAlex profile” entry indicates the number of authors for whom a corresponding OpenAlex profile has been found. Entries such as “Authors with OA matches \geq Scopus matches” refer to the number of authors for whom the number of works found in OpenAlex is greater than or equal to the number of works found in Scopus.

Statistic	Value
Total authors	172
Percentage of Authors with OA matches \geq Scopus matches	90.12%
Percentage of Authors with Scopus matches $>$ OA matches	9.88%
Percentage of Authors with at least one work missing only in OpenAlex	20.93%
Average number of works missing only in OpenAlex	3.44

Table 10: Overall statistics on personnel records from non bibliometric areas used in works coverage experiment. The “Authors with an OpenAlex profile” entry indicates the number of authors for whom a corresponding OpenAlex profile has been found. Entries such as “Authors with OA matches \geq Scopus matches” refer to the number of authors for whom the number of works found in OpenAlex is greater than or equal to the number of works found in Scopus.

Table 11: Overall statistics of works coverage experiment grouped by disciplinary sectors and ordered by the number of works found only on Scopus and not in OpenAlex, in descending order. “Avg Missing OA” column refer to the average number of works found only on Scopus and not in OpenAlex per disciplinary section.

Rank	COD_SSD	Total Missing OA	Total Authors	Avg Missing OA
1	IINF-05/A	43	49	2.05
2	CEAR-09/A	40	1	40.00
3	IIND-02/A	30	28	1.67
4	IIND-01/E	28	5	5.60
5	CEAR-06/A	25	16	2.78
6	IIND-01/D	24	7	4.80
7	IBIO-01/A	22	26	1.83
8	IINF-03/A	22	14	2.44
9	IIND-05/A	22	5	5.50
10	CEAR-08/C	21	6	21.00
11	IMAT-01/A	18	17	1.80
12	IIND-04/A	16	14	2.67
13	IIND-07/D	15	5	3.00

Rank	COD_SSD	Total Missing OA	Total Authors	Avg Missing OA
14	PHYS-03/A	13	19	1.86
15	IIND-03/A	12	17	2.00
16	CHEM-06/A	11	18	2.75
17	CEAR-05/A	11	12	2.20
18	CEAR-07/A	10	6	3.33
19	CEAR-04/A	9	14	1.29
20	IINF-01/A	9	25	1.29
21	CEAR-02/B	8	2	4.00
22	CEAR-03/C	8	8	2.67
23	IIND-08/A	8	9	2.00
24	IINF-04/A	8	6	2.00
25	IJET-01/A	7	9	2.33
26	IIND-03/C	7	4	2.33
27	IIND-08/B	6	6	2.00
28	CEAR-02/D	6	2	3.00
29	IIND-06/B	6	5	1.50
30	IIND-01/G	5	4	1.67
31	IIND-07/B	5	11	1.00
32	ICHI-01/A	5	3	2.50
33	GEOS-03/B	5	2	2.50
34	CEAR-03/B	5	3	2.50
35	CEAR-03/A	4	5	2.00
36	CEAR-02/A	4	6	1.33
37	IINF-02/A	3	6	1.00
38	MATH-05/A	3	8	1.00
39	CEAR-01/B	3	5	1.50
40	CEAR-10/A	3	3	1.50
41	IIND-01/F	2	6	2.00
42	GEOS-04/B	2	3	2.00
43	IIND-07/A	2	9	2.00
44	ICHI-02/A	2	5	1.00
45	ICHI-02/B	2	6	1.00
46	FIS/03	2	1	2.00
47	CEAR-08/D	2	3	2.00
48	ICHI-01/C	2	4	2.00
49	MATH-04/A	2	7	2.00
50	ICAR/03	2	2	1.00
51	PHIL-03/A	2	1	2.00
52	ICHI-01/B	1	2	1.00
53	IIND-06/A	1	8	1.00
54	IIND-01/C	1	1	1.00
55	PHYS-04/A	1	5	1.00
56	CEAR-12/A	1	4	1.00
57	MATH-06/A	1	4	1.00
58	BIOS-05/A	1	1	1.00
59	CEAR-08/A	1	1	1.00
60	CEAR-12/B	1	4	1.00
61	CEAR-01/A	1	2	1.00
62	IEGE-01/A	1	4	1.00
63	GEOG-01/B	1	2	1.00
64	ICAR/05	1	1	1.00

Rank	COD_SSD	Total Missing OA	Total Authors	Avg Missing OA
65	MATH-02/B	0	7	0.00
66	MATH-02/A	0	3	0.00
67	MATH-03/B	0	3	0.00
68	PHYS-02/A	0	3	0.00
69	IMIS-01/B	0	2	0.00
70	CEAR-11/B	0	1	0.00
71	ICAR/08	0	1	0.00
72	STAT-01/A	0	1	0.00
73	MATH-03/A	0	7	0.00
74	CEAR-08/B	0	1	0.00
75	ING-IND/22	0	1	0.00
76	ING-INF/03	0	3	0.00
77	CEAR-11/A	0	2	0.00
78	IIND-03/B	0	1	0.00
79	GSPS-08/B	0	1	0.00
80	CHEM-02/A	0	1	0.00
81	PHYS-05/B	0	1	0.00

Table 12: Overall statistics of works coverage experiment grouped by disciplinary sectors and ordered by the number of authors for whom the number of works found in OpenAlex is greater than or equal to the number of works found in Scopus, in descending order. “Total Missing OA” column refers to the total number of works found only on Scopus and not in OpenAlex per disciplinary section.

Rank	COD_SSD	% OA \geq Scopus	Total Authors	Total Missing OA
1	IIND-03/A	100.00	17	12
2	IIND-01/F	100.00	6	2
3	IINF-05/A	100.00	49	43
4	CEAR-04/A	100.00	14	9
5	ICHI-01/B	100.00	2	1
6	IBIO-01/A	100.00	26	22
7	CEAR-09/A	100.00	1	40
8	IIND-04/A	100.00	14	16
9	IINF-01/A	100.00	25	9
10	CEAR-02/B	100.00	2	8
11	IIND-07/D	100.00	5	15
12	CEAR-03/C	100.00	8	8
13	GEOS-04/B	100.00	3	2
14	IIND-01/G	100.00	4	5
15	IIND-07/B	100.00	11	5
16	IJET-01/A	100.00	9	7
17	IIND-06/A	100.00	8	1
18	PHYS-03/A	100.00	19	13
19	IIND-08/A	100.00	9	8
20	CEAR-06/A	100.00	16	25
21	CHEM-06/A	100.00	18	11
22	IIND-01/C	100.00	1	1
23	IINF-03/A	100.00	14	22
24	MATH-02/A	100.00	3	0
25	CEAR-05/A	100.00	12	11
26	IMAT-01/A	100.00	17	18

Rank	COD_SSD	% OA \geq Scopus	Total Authors	Total Missing OA
27	IIND-08/B	100.00	6	6
28	MATH-03/B	100.00	3	0
29	IIND-07/A	100.00	9	2
30	CEAR-08/C	100.00	6	21
31	ICHI-02/A	100.00	5	2
32	PHYS-02/A	100.00	3	0
33	CEAR-02/D	100.00	2	6
34	PHYS-04/A	100.00	5	1
35	IMIS-01/B	100.00	2	0
36	CEAR-03/A	100.00	5	4
37	CEAR-12/A	100.00	4	1
38	CEAR-07/A	100.00	6	10
39	FIS/03	100.00	1	2
40	CEAR-08/D	100.00	3	2
41	IIND-03/C	100.00	4	7
42	CEAR-02/A	100.00	6	4
43	IIND-01/D	100.00	7	24
44	MATH-06/A	100.00	4	1
45	BIOS-05/A	100.00	1	1
46	ICHI-01/C	100.00	4	2
47	IIND-06/B	100.00	5	6
48	CEAR-08/A	100.00	1	1
49	CEAR-12/B	100.00	4	1
50	ICHI-01/A	100.00	3	5
51	ICAR/03	100.00	2	2
52	ICAR/08	100.00	1	0
53	CEAR-01/A	100.00	2	1
54	STAT-01/A	100.00	1	0
55	CEAR-10/A	100.00	3	3
56	IEGE-01/A	100.00	4	1
57	MATH-03/A	100.00	7	0
58	CEAR-08/B	100.00	1	0
59	ING-IND/22	100.00	1	0
60	GEOG-01/B	100.00	2	1
61	GEOS-03/B	100.00	2	5
62	ING-INF/03	100.00	3	0
63	CEAR-03/B	100.00	3	5
64	IIND-03/B	100.00	1	0
65	PHIL-03/A	100.00	1	2
66	CHEM-02/A	100.00	1	0
67	ICAR/05	100.00	1	1
68	PHYS-05/B	100.00	1	0
69	IIND-02/A	89.29	28	30
70	MATH-05/A	87.50	8	3
71	MATH-02/B	85.71	7	0
72	MATH-04/A	85.71	7	2
73	IINF-04/A	83.33	6	8
74	IINF-02/A	83.33	6	3
75	ICHI-02/B	83.33	6	2
76	CEAR-01/B	80.00	5	3
77	IIND-01/E	80.00	5	28

Rank	COD_SSD	% OA \geq Scopus	Total Authors	Total Missing OA
78	CEAR-11/A	50.00	2	0
79	IIND-05/A	40.00	5	22
80	CEAR-11/B	0.00	1	0
81	GSPS-08/B	0.00	1	0

References

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2. M. Gionfriddo. `polito_fair_project`: Python tools for matching academic authors and works between iris, openalex, and scopus databases. GitHub repository, 2026. GitHub: https://github.com/jnfrdm/polito_FAIR_project. Version: main branch (accessed 2026-01-29).